

MULTI SCALE SIMULATION OF FLOW IN DRY FIBRE PLACEMENT PREFORMS

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ABSTRACT

Dry Fibre Placement (DFP) has a large potential for manufacturing load-related preforms at minimum scrap rate and fibre crimp. Yet, challenging impregnation behaviour of these preforms during Liquid Composite Moulding (LCM) imposes a need for further research to optimize preform structure for higher permeability. For full understanding of flow behaviour within these preforms, flow has to be considered on micro-scale (in between single fibres), on meso scale (in between single rovings or strands) and on macro scale (on scale of parts to be manufactured). While macro and meso scale can be measured in experiments or derived from filling times in real processes, micro scale is not easily assessable and accessible. Analytical approaches are limited to regular fibre arrangements (square and hexagonal) that are strongly differing from real arrangements.

The present work deals with application of a numerical solver to random fibre arrangements to determine micro permeability transverse to the fibre orientation, for later use in meso- and macro scaled models. As a premise for reliable calculation, guidelines for boundary conditions as well as size and resolution of the Representative Volume Element are elaborated in the course of this work.

Calculated out-of-plane micro-permeabilities are subsequently compared to real experiments and show good accordance. The influence of binder particles on micro permeability has not yet been conclusively clarified.

1. INTRODUCTION

Today's applications for fibre reinforced polymer composites (FRPC) demand high mechanical performance values at lowest possible weight. To overcome the drawback of part costs that are usually significantly higher than those of metal parts, current developments and research aim at reducing manufacturing costs. As a consequence, even industries traditionally relying on high performance parts manufactured in prepreg-autoclave technique, such as aeronautics, investigate possibilities to use Liquid Composite Moulding (LCM) processes such as they have a great potential for cost-efficient large volume production of high performance composite parts [1, 2]. For these processes, dry near-net shape preforms are manufactured (preformed) to be later on impregnated with a resin system in order to obtain the finished parts. One possibility to overcome the drawbacks of large scrap rates and to use load-path related fiber orientation is using direct preforming technologies such as Dry Fibre Placement (DFP), sometimes also referred to as Automated Dry Fibre Placement (AFP).

DFP allows the manufacturing of a near-net shape preform directly out of rovings within a single process step. In this method, several rovings are placed on a surface and can be oriented according to the designed load paths. This process, however, requires a method for layer fixation. One possible solution is the application of powdery binder material (thermoplastic or thermoset) to the rovings. During the layup process, the binder is melted and afterwards a compaction roll compacts the rovings, fixes them on the tool or joins them with the already laid preform, and cools down the binder leading to solidification and fixation. By applying multiple tracks and layers of rovings onto the tool, a complex preform with adapted fibre and mass distribution according to the relevant load paths can be produced. Besides the low-waste preform manufacturing, material savings can also be achieved by

enabling completely new designs with this technique. For example, a direct integration of load introduction elements, core materials, or functional elements is possible.

While material efficiency and manufacturing flexibility of DFP preforms are very advantageous, the processing behaviour in the subsequent impregnation step is quite challenging. This is due to the relatively small permeability, which at similar fibre volume content can be 1-2 orders of magnitude smaller than the permeability of a woven or non-crimp fabric. In previous works, the authors have shown that the out-of-plane permeability of preforms manufactured by DFP can be impacted by various modifications of preform structure [3]. As stitching of preforms led to the highest increase of out-of-plane permeability, a systematic study of the influence of sewing parameters on out-of-plane permeability and mechanical performance has been conducted [4], showing that an increase of permeability by a factor of more than factor 30 is possible.

Experimental characterization of permeability is usually limited to measuring overall permeability of a textile or a stack of textiles. Furthermore, there are large experimental efforts to manufacture the measurement samples and the assessable parameter range is limited by time and economic constraints. For this purpose, it is expedient to involve simulative approaches allowing determination of permeability at different scales to consider all effects possibly influencing overall permeability as well as broadening the parameter range. What is more, even material configurations that cannot be manufactured using state of the art machinery can be simulated allowing design of future materials.

2. STATE OF THE ART AND THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

2.1. State of the art for modelling of impregnation behaviour of DFP preforms

Concerning the impregnation behaviour of DFP preforms, the main focus of previous research works was to estimate the influence of layup-induced effects on later impregnation steps. Recent research of Aziz et al. [5] concentrated on the simulative modelling of permeability of DFP preforms with gaps. Their basic assumption is that flow velocity within channels resulting from the inserted gaps is significantly higher than flow velocity within the surrounding dense fibre structure and thus flow is only calculated within these gaps. Still, the gap size range in which this is applicable is not mentioned despite this approach is unable to describe preforms without gaps, as the resulting permeability would be zero. Another recent research work [6] also deals with gaps introduced to optimize permeability, and the variability of observed gap width differing from intended gap width leading to a variability of permeability.

In other research work, the method of creating roving gaps is partly complemented with highly permeable fleece layers between the roving layers to ensure complete impregnation [7].

To overcome the limitations of the above mentioned models and in order to be able to describe the impregnation behaviour of any kind of structural variation inserted for the purpose of higher permeability, the present work deals with development of permeability simulation methodology on micro-scale, i.e. on level of single fibres to transfer these to meso and macro level using a multi-scale model at later stages.

2.2. Theoretical background for analytical and simulative modelling of permeability

When modelling permeability of preforms intended for use in composites manufacturing, several scales of flow and their interactions have to be taken into account. Following the bottom-up principle, we will be using the following definitions for description of flow in this work:

- Micro level flow describes flow in between single fibres, i.e. inside a roving or comparable structure of fibres that are nearly aligned (typically μm)
- Meso level flow describes flow on scale of rovings or fibre bundles (typically mm or cm)
- Macro level flow describes flow on scale of the manufactured part (cm /m)

2.2.1. Modelling of micro flow

To describe permeability within bundles of aligned fibres, a variety of analytical models have been developed. Using Darcy's law [8] describing flow within porous sand beds for a saturated case, permeability of a given material can be calculated when viscosity of the fluid, pressure drop and flow speed through given dimensions are known. Yet, this law does not allow determination of a material's permeability without conducting measurements.

Starting from the geometry of the perfused material, one approach to model permeability is the Kozeny-Carman-equation [9, 10]. It has initially been developed for beds of spherical particles and relies on experimental determination of a shape factor, the constants K_0 and K_1 have to be determined experimentally with validity of the results strictly limited to the measured material and fibre-volume-fraction [11]. Furthermore, there is no distinction between flow along and perpendicular to fibres. For this reason, Gebart [12] developed an analytical approach to describe the permeability of fibre beds in square and hexagonal packing for flow along fibres and perpendicular to it using integration of a velocity profile over a varying flow cross section obtained in a representative 2D cell. These models are still widely used in describing micro permeability. The main limitation results from the assumption of square or hexagonal packing which is not the case in real microstructures.

For this reason, this kind of problem is often approached using numerical methods, i.e. modelling fibre arrangements and solving a flow problem using methods with the help of computer-implemented solvers. There is a large range of possible methods to solve e.g. Navier-Stokes equations on a given structure, each varying in assumptions for generation of grids and boundary conditions as well as computational efficiency. Use of Lattice Boltzmann method [13] involves numerical solving of the Boltzmann equation on a grid involving interaction between physical particles. The Navier-Stokes equation can be derived from the Boltzmann kinetic equation. Boundary-Element-Method [14–17] constructs a mesh over the surfaces to be modelled and is most efficient for problems with a small surface/volume ratio [18]. The immersed boundary method [19] solves unsteady Navier-Stokes equations on a Cartesian grid while boundary conditions are derived from surfaces fitted to the bodies. Computational Fluid Dynamic (CFD) solvers solve discretized physics equations in an Eulerian scheme [20] and have been used in a variety of works, as well [21–25].

In this work, a LIR-tree approach for solving the stationary Stokes equations will be used, which is implemented in GeoDict software [26] and will be further described in chapter 3.2.

2.2.2. Modelling of meso flow

Calculating meso flow means determining mean permeability including several features of a dry preform structure, e.g. permeability within a roving and permeability caused by flow between single rovings. This means that the calculated value for flow is an averaged or assembled value resulting from two different scales. As standard textile reinforcement materials such as woven fabrics or NCF possess large flow channels mostly determining total permeability of the material [3, 4], a very common assumption involves modelling of meso-structure with rovings detailed as non-porous solid materials with a permeability of 0 [5] or an assigned permeability which often refers to the models introduced by Gebart [12]. It is obvious that this assumption can only be valid as long as flow caused by micro-permeability is significantly lower than flow caused by meso flow channels as already introduced by Pillai et. al. [27] who stated that low permeability zones can only be neglected in total flow calculation, if their effective permeability is less than 10% compared to high permeability zones at 50% total FVC. Hence, for DFP structures without present gaps allowing fluid flow, the assumption of impermeable tows is at least inaccurate.

When building up a meso-model with the premise of exact reproduction of flow on micro and meso scale, very large and thus computationally expensive models have to be built as an excessive number of fibres with a diameter range of some μm have to be detailed within a domain covering several mm or cm to be a representative volume. For this reason, it is expedient to determine sufficiently exact mean values for micro-permeability and insert them into a larger-scaled meso model for computation of permeability without the need of detailing single micro level geometric features.

2.2.3. Modelling of macro flow

Macro flow is usually considered when estimating filling time and behaviour of a given preform in a cavity for part manufacturing in an LCM process. The values used for these predictions are usually determined using permeability measurements of textile stacks similar to those used in the LCM process. Macro flow will not be further considered within this paper.

3. DEVELOPMENT OF A METHODOLOGY FOR MICRO PERMEABILITY SIMULATION

The present work deals with development of permeability simulation methodology on micro-scale, i.e. on level of single fibres to transfer these to meso and macro level using a multi-scale model at later stages. The development and evaluation of a set of methods, boundary conditions and parameters will be discussed in the following sections.

After development, the results from permeability calculations using these methods will be compared to real experiments determining out-of-plane permeability of DFP preforms [4] in section 4.2.

3.1. Generation of fibre structures

Fibre structures for this work have been generated with the GeoDict Module FibreGeo [26]. The algorithm sheds fibres in the desired fibre volume content with random center points into the domain. Subsequently, overlap is removed by randomly shifting fibres by 1 voxel until the set maximum residual overlap is left. Starting point for generation is a random seed used to generate random numbers. That means that for same random seed and same parameters, the same structure will be generated. When varying the random seed without changing the other parameters, another random structure fulfilling the parameters will be generated. With this method, unique random fibre arrangements can be generated without a minimum separation distance. By changing the random seed from simulation to simulation, statistical coverage of varying fibre arrangements can be achieved. In real structures, each 2D-section through the structure would represent one random fibre arrangement and permeability for the 3D case would be near the averaged permeability of the single 2D sections when assuming that a small part of flow occurs perpendicular to it. The computational domain is generated in voxels, i.e. cubic volume elements of equal size. Each voxel is assigned with a material ID, in this case, a voxel can either be part of a fibre or part of the porous space between fibres. In this work, the assumption of parallel fibres has been made and thus depth of the model (direction of fibre length) is only kept to avoid boundary effects for nearly 2D models.

3.2. Solver for computation of fluid flow

The solver used to compute flow through fibre structures solves the stationary Stokes equations on a grid of voxels. For solving the flow problem, a measurement grid is generated differing from the voxel geometry to be very fine at borders of solid elements for good description of the boundary layer at fibre edges while coarsening pure porous regions with little gradients in flow speed and pressure. To ensure a good transition between these areas, certain restrictions in neighbour size ratios apply. In total, this method is very memory- and runtime efficient [28, 29]. An example of an adapted grid for calculation of transverse flow through a field of circular fibres is depicted in Figure 1.

The solver has been proven to compute reliable results on generic structures with known analytically determinable permeability as well as real porous rock materials [20] (referred to as VBS-3). In the calculations done in this work, a pressure drop of 0.02 Pa has been set and permeabilities have been computed using an incompressible fluid. As a creeping flow of a Newtonian fluid is described, pressure drop and fluid viscosity could be changed without influencing calculated permeability, only calculated flow velocity would be changed. It has been checked that also when varying these parameters, no change in permeability calculation occurs. For the stopping criterion, an error bound criterion has been chosen with a tolerance of 3%. This criterion estimates the asymptotic convergence of permeability values over the conducted iterations and stops the simulation if the calculated permeability is within 3% of the estimated final permeability.

Figure 1: Example of variable grid structure for flow transverse to circular fibres

3.3. Choice of boundary conditions

For computation of flow, an assumption of flow conditions at the boundaries of the flow domain has to be done. Wise choice of boundary conditions is crucial for realistic calculation results. Several boundary conditions have to be chosen and will be detailed in this subsection.

In flow direction, the boundary conditions periodic, symmetric and periodic with implicit in- and outlet can be chosen. For periodic boundary conditions, the domain is implicitly repeated in flow direction. As random fibre structures considered for calculation of transverse permeability in this paper do not possess periodicity, there is a tendency to calculate low permeability values. This can be explained by the necessity of presence of a flow channel on the inlet as well as on the outlet that coincide to allow fluid flow. In comparison, for symmetric boundary conditions, the domain is implicitly mirrored leading to the mentioned coincidence of flow channels at inlet and outlet. While this is much more realistic than periodic boundary conditions for this case, computing time is three times as much for the considered domain. Another option is using in- and outlet regions implicitly added before and after the computed domain to homogenize flow between periodically repeated structures. Calculated permeability of periodic boundary conditions with implicit in- and outlet matches symmetric boundary conditions while achieving the shortest computation time. For this reason, periodic boundary condition with implicit in- and outlet regions will be chosen in this work.

Similar to boundary conditions in flow direction, several boundary conditions **transverse to flow direction** have to be chosen. Periodic, symmetric and no-slip boundary conditions show a differing behaviour. Periodic boundary conditions implicitly repeat the domain at the transverse boundaries. In case of flow channels within the structure that are prevalent in tangential direction to main flow, higher permeabilities will be computed as flow out of the domain can “re-enter” the domain at the other side, however, this will not occur in real structures. For this reason, symmetric boundary conditions appear more realistic as no flow crosses the domain boundaries due to pressure equilibrium tangential to flow direction at boundaries. One more possible boundary condition would be no-slip at the domain boundary. As the whole tangential boundary acts as a “friction-wall”, lower total permeabilities will be computed. Furthermore, the computational effort is significantly increased. For these reasons, symmetric boundary conditions tangential to flow direction are chosen throughout this work.

Similar to real structures, a no-slip **boundary condition at fibre edges** is chosen leading to a boundary layer with velocity gradient.

3.4. Consideration of statistical deviation of computed permeability of random fibre arrangements

Computed permeabilities for random fibre arrangements exhibit inherent deviation of results. To compute an appropriate average, a representative sample of the statistical population has to be taken. For this reason, permeability values of 1000 random fibre arrangements have been computed to examine statistical distribution of computed values. Shapiro Wilk test for normal distribution showed a correlation of 99%. Hence, we assume that computing permeabilities for 10 random fibre structures for one parameter set is a sufficient sample to state mean value and standard distribution. This will be further verified in chapter 3.6.

3.5. Determination of needed voxel resolution for accurate computation of micro permeability

For accurate computation of flow within a structure, discretisation has to be sufficiently fine. When talking about circular fibres in a domain that is discretised using cubic voxels, it is obvious that voxel size will need to be significantly smaller than fibre diameter in order to achieve nearly round fibres. Coarse voxels will lead to unround and thus “rough” fibres hindering flow transverse to them. The flow solver itself does not rely on the generated voxel structure, as an adaptive grid is used refining detail of calculation in areas with large gradients and coarsening detail of calculation in areas where flow is homogeneous for faster information propagation in the whole structure for faster convergence. At a certain voxel resolution, the mean values of computed permeabilities are expected to converge as no further improvement of calculation exactness is reached. In the conducted variation of voxel size, it can be seen that there is a convergency effect of permeabilities at a ratio of voxel size / fibre diameter of about 1/10. In the case of the assumed 7 μm fibre diameter, this means voxel sizes at or below 0.7 μm . For larger voxel sizes, it can be stated that high standard deviations occur, the lower threshold of the 1σ confidence interval is already below 0 as single calculations deliver a permeability of 0 with no through path. This effect becomes even more important at very high FVC, as pore space between fibres is further reduced and coarse fibre reproduction will hinder flow transverse to fibres.

Figure 2: Simulated transverse permeability at FVC 55% depending on voxel size of the computation domain; visualization of domain at voxel sizes 0.3 and 1.6 μm

3.6. Determination of needed RVE size for accurate computation of micro permeability

A Representative Volume Element (RVE) contains a structure being typical for the material to be modelled with the premise of containing “a sufficient number of microstructural elements so that boundary conditions at the surface of the composite do not affect the effective properties” [30]. This definition has been introduced for computation of mechanical behaviour of composites but can be transferred to flow computation.

When considering regular fibre arrangements as in [12], an RVE can be very small as this very periodic arrangement can be sufficiently described using just some fibres. For random arrangements however, a large imaginable quantity of inter-fibre-pore-spaces is possible and thus, a certain number of fibres have to be contained within an RVE to reproduce real fibre arrangement variations such as

local accumulations of fibres or larger pores between such regions. There is a certain correlation between statistical variation of permeabilities as depicted in Figure 3 and size of an RVE as larger considered RVEs inherently incorporate the variations of several imaginable structures within one calculation.

In conducted simulations, RVE size has been varied with 256^2 , 356^2 and 456^2 voxels perpendicular to fibre direction with constant 64 voxels in fibre direction with a voxel size of $0.5 \mu\text{m}$. It has been checked that choosing larger domains than 64 voxels in thickness direction did not lead to a change in computed permeability. 251, 490 and 785 single fibres were contained in the RVE for the three chosen different domain sizes. The result is shown in Figure 3. It can be seen that already at 10 single simulations, the average converges towards the same average calculated on 1000 single simulations. For the larger RVEs, a better and faster convergency of the average can be observed. This can be explained by the larger number of single fibres contained and thus the increased degree of statistical coverage contained in single random fibre arrangements. For the smallest RVE, there is a higher probability of rogue single results such as locally blocked structures delivering a value of 0 or local channels delivering high values affecting the average.

Figure 3: Consideration of needed number of simulations for convergency of average calculated permeability

4. COMPARISON OF COMPUTED WITH MEASURED PERMEABILITIES

After modelling micro permeability using the methods introduced above, the obtained values can be compared with permeabilities determined in real experiments. As real DFP preforms also contain larger scaled binder particles, two methods of incorporating them in flow simulation are compared here.

4.1. Calculation of meso permeability with binder particles on micro level

As discussed above, measured out-of-plane permeability of unstitched DFP preforms can be mostly modelled by assuming micro flow in between single fibres as no meso flow channels are present. Yet, binder particles used for cohesion of the preform during layup and handling have to be considered as they might hinder flow within the preform. For this reason, an RVE following the guidelines mentioned above has been modelled and ellipsoid binder particles with the calculated volume percentage of 3.7% as present in the real preform have been added. For particle sizes, measurements from [3] have been used. The single steps of model generation are depicted in Figure 4. As it can be seen, the minimum RVE size requirements determined for pure micro permeability calculation have

been exceeded to incorporate more binder particles in each single RVE. In total, $366 \times 549 \times 366$ voxels with a size of $0.7 \mu\text{m}$ each are contained. Just like in the considerations above, statistical coverage is achieved by conducting structure generation using 10 different random seeds per parameter set.

Figure 4: Modelling of a preform structure with binder, example of cross-section through resulting flow field shows binder particles hindering flow

To put the computed values in a comparable context, Figure 5 shows a comparison of out-of-plane permeability values obtained in [4] to those computed in this work. It is assumed that the pure UD unstitched preform in the previous work has a comparable micro-structure to the computed micro-structure. Compared to the experimental measurements of out-of-plane permeability, simulated values tend to be about three times higher at 50% FVC while there is a very good match at 60% FVC. A possible explanation for this is fibre mobility in real structures at the lower FVC that leads to hydrodynamic compaction and thus reduction of permeability compared to immobile fibres in simulation that are not prone for hydrodynamic compaction. Furthermore, the effect of binder particles leading to inhomogeneities has not been considered here. It can be seen in the diagram that permeability after adding the binder particles is about 10% lower than without binder.

The relationship between binder volume fraction in the preform and total permeability in transverse to fibre direction can be considered nearly linear in these calculations. When comparing these results to the experiments conducted in [3], there is a contradicting trend as experimental measurements showed a slight increase of permeability with increasing binder amount. However, in the simulations, a reduction of permeability has been observed which is caused by reduced porosity. Hence, it can be supposed that the real-life effect of binder particles leading to preform inhomogeneity and thus to larger inter-fibre flow channels already suspected in the previous work has a larger influence on permeability than reduced porosity as assumed here. In this simulation model, binder particles have been added without movement of fibres and thus not causing any inhomogeneity.

Hence, in further steps, a full 3D model has to be considered incorporating fibre features such as misorientation, undulation or tortuosity. Still, the parameters for these effects have to be obtained using methods such as μCT and generation of the domain might be significantly more complex.

4.2. Calculation of meso permeability with binder particles with solid tows

It has been mentioned before that it is more effective to model larger domains with a multiscale approach than modelling all details. For this reason, computed permeabilities for micro flow have been used as an input material parameter for modelling of a porous solid RVE. Binder particles have been added statistically as overlap material hindering flow just like in chapter 4.1. As no single fibres have to be resolved in the model, voxel size is only limited by size of binder particles (largest diameter of ellipsoid $125 \mu\text{m}$ instead of fibre diameter $7 \mu\text{m}$), thus, the model has a total size of 256^3 voxels with a size of $10 \mu\text{m}$. In Figure 5, it can be seen that for this multiscale approach, the relationship between binder volume fraction in the preform and total permeability in transverse to fibre direction is nearly linear, as well. Compared to the results with detailed fibre modelling with and without binder, the results of the multiscale approach appear to be just in the middle.

Figure 5: Comparison of experimental and simulative determination of permeability perpendicular to fibres at FVC from 50 to 60%. Experimental values from [4]

5. SUMMARY

In this work, numerical computation of micro-permeability transverse to fibre direction has been considered. It has been shown:

- When calculating permeabilities on small random RVEs, a statistical distribution similar to a Gaussian distribution of calculated values can be observed. This leads to the assumption that considering 10 single RVEs per parameter set ensures sufficient statistical coverage to estimate a micro-permeability.
- In order to sufficiently detail geometric features of single fibres, voxel size has to be chosen smaller than 1/10th of fibre diameter. When using the statistical approach, the RVE has to contain a minimum of ≈ 785 fibres.
- For further enhancement of the model, binder particles similar to those present in real structures can be added on meso level. The two approaches of either modelling micro permeability with contained binder particles or using calculated micro permeability as input for a solid tow meso model show similar results within 5%. Compared to real measurements of out-of-plane permeability, simulated values tend to be about three times higher at 50% FVC while there is a very good match at 60% FVC. A possible explanation for this is fibre mobility in real structures at the lower FVC that leads to hydrodynamic compaction and thus reduction of permeability compared to immobile fibres in simulation that are not prone for hydrodynamic compaction. Furthermore, the effect of binder particles leading to inhomogeneities has not been considered here. Still, the achieved accuracy for micro permeability is well within a useful range and can be used for further simulations.

After detailing these basic requirements for simulation of transverse micro permeability in random fibre arrangements, these values can subsequently be used for modelling larger scaled models with micro permeability as input parameter. This will allow assessing the effects already observed with stitched / tufted preform structures and expanding the parameter range in order to optimize permeability to the values required for processing without excessively impeding mechanical performance.

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